

Long Term Thermal Cycling of SCS-6/Ti-15-3 Metal Matrix Composite

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Abstract

Four sets of SCS-6/Ti-15-3 metal matrix composite (MMC) tensile specimens were thermal cycled from room temperature to four different maximum cycling temperatures; 500°C, 600°C, 650°C, and 700°C. The thermal cycling apparatus allowed for nearly a "square wave" thermal profile which held the specimens at the maximum temperatures for 25, 50, and 75 hours at the given number of cycles of 500, 1000, and 1500, respectively. Tensile testing revealed a consistent decrease in the ultimate tensile strength of the specimens with increasing maximum cycling temperature levels. Microstructural examination revealed that no cracking had occurred and only the Ti-15-3 matrix exhibited a noticeable change. The reduction in the tensile strength of the thermal cycled MMC is attributed to the softening of the metal matrix, especially to the metal adjacent to the fibers.

Introduction

In order to achieve high performance aerospace structures, materials possessing high strengths with low densities (high specific strengths), combined with high temperature resistance, are required. This is one reason for the relatively recent development of metal matrix composites (MMC) systems. Ceramic fibers in typical MMC's possess a coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) much lower than the metal matrix. This mismatch of CTE's has the potential to cause cracking whenever this material is thermally cycled due to the strain on the fiber-matrix interface. This has been observed in various studies which have shown that accumulated damage can occur due to thermal cycling and, in certain cases, have resulted in the reduction of their mechanical properties [1-6]. In these particular studies, the MMC's were thermally cycled at elevated temperatures without external loading which caused a measurable elongation in the longitudinal fiber direction creating porosity and cracking at the fiber-matrix reaction zone. Both of these damage types were determined to be the direct result of CTE mismatch between the fiber and the matrix.

In most thermal cycling studies the specimens were exposed to the maximum temperatures for short time periods by using either "sine wave" or "saw tooth" temperature profiles. But in actual applications, these materials would likely be subjected to a thermal profile resembling a "square wave" with a dwell time at the maximum cycling temperature. This would then subject the speci-

mens to a combination of sustained high temperature effects and thermal cycling and presumably give rise to severer damage.

Experimental Procedure

The SCS-6 fiber/Ti-15-3-3-3 (Ti-15-3) MMC system was used for this study. This alloy is generally limited to applications below 550°C - 600°C because of alloy embrittlement due to oxygen diffusion through the surface [7]. The SCS-6 fibers were manufactured at Textron using a chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process starting with a 33 μm diameter carbon filament, upon which SiC was deposited. After the SiC was deposited, a complex outer coating of SiC and Carbon giving the fiber and overall diameter of 145 μm [8]. This outer coating is applied to reduce the surface flaws, allow for easier handling, and to limit the reaction zone between the fibers and the titanium matrix.

The reaction zone appears in almost all SiC/Ti MMC's as an interface which initially occurs as a result of processing or consolidation of the metal and fibers into MMC's. The metal matrix consolidation is usually done at high temperatures (1100°C) where the outer coating of the fibers reacts with the titanium in the matrix creating a zone which can start as low as 727°C. This reaction zone is composed of small particulates which consist of TiC adjacent to the fiber and Ti₅Si₃ next to the matrix. In addition, some small "islands" of reaction products usually exist within the matrix adjacent to the fibers. This reaction zone is the fiber-matrix interface that transfers the loads from the matrix into the fibers and can greatly influence the mechanical behavior of the MMC [8].

The tensile specimens were fabricated from panels manufactured by Textron and donated by Boeing for this study. The panels consisted of eight alternating foils of Ti-15-3 with SCS-6 fibers in unidirectional orientation. The panels were determined to have a fiber volume fraction of approximately 36% -40% based on previous analysis by Boeing. No heat treatment was given to the panels prior to fabrication or testing of the specimens. Specimens were cut from the panels using electrical discharge machining (EDM) because usual machining processes could cause excessive fiber pullout in the curvatures of the specimen shape. No attempt was made to grind off any heat affected zone that may have developed during the EDM process. The tensile specimens were in a flatbar type configuration with the fiber orientated in the longitudinal direction. They were 76.2 mm long by 12.7 mm wide with a gage region 5 mm wide by 12.7 mm long.

The specimens were thermally cycled, unloaded, into and out of a 100 mm diameter vertical furnace tube heated using four SiC heating rods. Two thermocouples were used for temperature control; one was placed adjacent to the furnace wall for power supply control, and the other attached to the cycling specimens to determine the appropriate settings for the furnace power supply. The specimens were attached to a rod that was moved into and out of the furnace by means of a motor/pulley system using a mechanical timer.

Each thermal cycle combined a heat cycle, approximately 5 minutes, with a 7 minute non-forced air cooling cycle. The overall thermal cycle temperature profile resembled a "square wave" having an approximately 3 minute dwell at the maximum thermal cycle temperature (T_{max}), Fig. 1. The specimens were exposed to T_{max} for 25, 50 and 75 hours for; 500, 1000, and 1500 cycles, respectively.

Four maximum elevated cycling temperatures were used; 500°C, 600°C, 650°C, and 700°C. Three specimens were cycled at each maximum cycling temperature with the removal of one specimen after every 500 cycles. In addition, dimensions of the specimens were determined periodically during the thermal cycling testing.

Figure 1. Typical Thermal Cycling Temperature Profile

Results

The results of the tensile testing are shown in Fig. 2 with each point representing the results of one tensile specimen test. The failure stresses appear to decrease consistently with increasing maximum cycling temperatures by about 250 MPa for each different setting of T_{max} .

Figure 2. Residual Tensile Strength of Thermal Cycled Specimens

Samples of specimens were examined metallographically revealing a greater change in the matrix microstructures with increasing maximum cycling temperatures when compared with the uncycled specimens. The uncycled specimen exhibited a typical as-received Ti-15-3 microstructure (Fig. 3a) which contained a few dark blotchy regions distributed throughout the matrix. These regions were probably the solute lean, coherent β' phase [9].

Figure 3. a) Microstructure of the Uncycled Specimen
 b) Microstructure of the 700° C/1500 Cycled Specimen

Starting with the 500°C specimens, the α phase began to precipitate in a very fine needle form from the β' phase. (Fig. 3b). These precipitates gradually increased in dimensions as seen in the 600°C/1500 cycle microstructure then became extremely coarse as the maximum cycling and temperatures were increased to 700°C/1500 cycles. The largest α phase precipitates were located adjacent to the grain boundaries and the fibers. However, no cracks or other damage was observed in the matrix of any of the specimens.

In addition, an oxide layer covering the specimens was observed which increased in thickness with higher maximum cycling temperatures and cycles. But even at the most extreme case, 700°C at 1500 cycles, the oxidation did not penetrate beyond the first fiber layer.

The fiber-matrix reaction zones do not appear to change with either increasing cycles or maximum temperatures. In addition, no debonding or damage was observed at the reaction zone. The fibers were neither affected by the thermal cycling, other than cracks observed in a few fibers which corresponded directly to the mechanical test machine grip impressions made on the surface of the specimens.

Evaluation of the fracture surface morphology of the tensile specimens revealed no significant differences regardless of the cycling conditions. The matrix adjacent to the fibers formed sharp ridges consistent with plastic flow. Dimpling, also indicative of plastic overload, was present on all of the matrix surfaces whether it was on the ridges adjacent to the fibers or between the fibers. The reaction zones on the other hand, appeared to have fractured in a brittle mode. These materials did not adhere consistently to either the outer coatings, on the fibers, or the matrix. Furthermore, a fracture region between the carbon fiber core and the SiC region was clearly observed. This interface was not easily characterized in the metallographic examination. It appears to be similar to the fiber-matrix reaction zone in that it adhered to both fracture surfaces inconsistently.

The metallographic mounts of the uncycled and the 700°C/1500 cycled specimen were placed in a scanning electron microscope for further evaluation of the reaction zone. Like the optical examination, no significant microstructural changes could be detected at a 7500X magnification. The only

notable change was the configuration of the outer layer of the fiber. The uncycled coating on the fiber appeared to be in three layers probably composed of equal compositions based on the signal strength detected by the SEM which corresponding to their atomic numbers. The 700°C/1500 specimen reaction zone appeared to have only two such layers but it had the same total thickness (approximately 4.5 μm) as the un-cycled reaction zone. The reaction zones also appeared to have same average thickness and possessing similar jagged appearance.

Most of the specimens developed overall dimensional changes during the cycling. All of the recorded specimen dimensions generally increased with increasing maximum cycling temperatures and cycles. The maximum dimensional change was 0.215 inch on the 700°C/1500 specimen at the gage thickness. However, the length or longitudinal direction measurements did not increase consistently with the other measurements. A comparison of the micrometer measurements with the oxide measurements from the micrographs, indicated that the specimen growth was due to the oxidation products.

Discussion

Since no general damage or porosity was observed, this would suggest that a microstructural or chemical change occurred within the composite material which would cause a reduction in the tensile properties. There are three primary material components within the MMC; the fibers, reaction zone, and the Ti-15-3 matrix, which can affect the properties of the composite system.

From observations, the fibers did not appear to have been affected either by the increase in the number of cycles or the maximum cycling temperature. No cracks or microstructural changes were observed in the cross sections, either in the core or the bulk of the fibers, which would suggest that the thermal cycling did not effect the fiber material to any noticeable degree. This is consistent with other studies that have shown that these fiber types by themselves exhibited little change in their mechanical properties up to approximately 1100°C [10]. Since these specimens were cycled at considerably lower temperatures it would appear that the fibers themselves were not affected.

The fibers' strength within the matrix can be greatly affected by the properties of the fiber-matrix reaction zone. Yet observations of the reaction zones did not reveal any microstructural changes and these regions were probably not effected by the thermal cycling. In other work, [11] it was reported that the reaction zone of the SCS-6/Ti-15-3 system can actually increase in strength under specific thermal ageing conditions., In a SCS-6/Ti-15-3 composite system the interfacial shear strength increased from approximately 118 MPa to 131 Mpa, at 800°C from 12 hours to 50 hours. This would increase the overall strength of the fibers and therefore the composite as it would allow for better transfer of the loads to the fibers. But since the composite material in this study exhibited a decrease in strength, any possible changes to the interfacial shear strength of the reaction zone did not seem to have any affect.

Since the fibers and the reaction zone did not appear to change the mechanical properties of the MMC, the only component of the composite that most likely contributed to the reduced strength in the composite was the matrix. Heat treatment studies of SCS-6/Ti-15-3 have shown that the matrix will decrease in strength over time due to phase changes [9]. The study compared un-reinforced Ti-15-3 alloy properties to SCS-6/Ti-15-3 composite properties by ageing the materials at temperatures ranging from 300°C to 700°C for 24 hours. It revealed that, based on hardness measurements, the strength of the MMC would increase to a plateau between 400°C and 500°C and then decrease with increasing ageing temperatures. In a related study [12], this MMC was aged for the times and temperatures shown in Table 1 with the resulting ultimate tensile strengths:

Table 1

<u>Temperature/Time</u>	<u>UTS (MPa)</u>
As Fabricated	1572 ± 125
500°C/50 hr	1728 ± 130
500°C/100 hr	1607 ± 104
800°C/12 hr	1331 ± 41
800°C/50 hr	1269 ± 212

The thermal treatments shown above most likely causes the solute rich alloy to separate into solute-rich β and α solute-lean β' phases prior to the precipitation of the α phase from the β' crystals. The α phase provides strengthening to the alloy but requires long ageing time due to the slow formation kinetics. Ti-15-3 is also susceptible to grain boundary formation of the α phase. This is due to the nucleation kinetics of the α in the grain boundaries which is not as sensitive to β stabilizers as the kinetics for the formation of intergranular α [13]. Additional ageing coarsens the α phase which in turn reduces its strain to failure and eventually reducing the overall strength of the alloy.

Since the residual strengths of the specimens doesn't change appreciably for a given maximum thermal cycling temperature level after the first 500 cycles, it appears that the reduction in strength of this MMC occurred during the first 500 cycles.

In comparison to a similar thermal cycling study [14], the tensile specimens exhibited no appreciable change in the residual strength even after undergoing more cycles than specimens had undergone for this paper. In that study, two sets of tensile specimens were cycled from 149°C to 427°C and from 149°C to 649°C, for up to 16,750 cycles yet the tensile strengths varied between 1750 MPa and 1900 MPa with no correlation to the number of cycles or the maximum cycling temperature level. The composite lay-up of eight plies was similar to the one used for this study however their tensile specimens were rectangle in shape, 12.7 mm by 177 mm, with no specific gage length or necked region. In addition, these specimens started cycling in the "as-received" condition and in an unloaded condition. However, the specimens were cycled using a 48 second cycle "saw tooth" temperature profile with no dwell time at either the high or low temperatures. It appears that their specimens were probably not overaged due to the limited time at the elevated temperature and therefore did not suffer a reduction in tensile strength. The different cycling thermal profiles used in these studies may be responsible for the discrepancy of the results.

In another study [15] using a similar thermal cycling temperature profile, 33.3 hours at T_{max} , the reduction in the residual strength of the specimens (SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V) was attributed to changes of the matrix, primarily oxygen embrittlement, which subsequently caused a degradation of the fibers.

A calculation was performed on the tensile data using the rule of mixtures, Eqn (1), to determine whether the reduction in the matrix strength could be directly correlated to the overall composite strength:

$$\sigma_c = V_f (\sigma_f) + (1 - V_f) \sigma_m \quad (1)$$

The matrix and fiber strength values used for the calculations were obtained from previous studies [9,16]. As seen in Fig. 5, the results do not correspond generally for the data beyond the 600°C strength levels. There are two possible reasons for this discrepancy. One is that the rule of mixtures is a simple model that may not take into account the interactions of other variables that could affect this specific composite, such as the interfacial shear strength. Another reason would most likely be the nonuniform matrix changes such as those observed in Fig. 3b. The precipitate lean

region surrounding the fibers would exhibit a lower mechanical strength due to fewer precipitates which would reduce the overall matrix strength. The effective matrix flow stress that is influential in governing the fracture of a MMC is that of the matrix adjacent to the fiber. Thus if σ_m in equation (1) is replaced by the matrix flow stress of the soft region surrounding the fiber, then the rule of mixtures suggests that the strength of the composite is reduced due to the existence of the soft region.

Figure 5. Plot of the Rule of Mixtures Predictions Compared to the Experimental Data

Conclusions

1. In regards to the fibers, matrix and the reaction zone, only the microstructure of the Ti-15-3 matrix exhibited a change which can be related primarily to the exposure of the specimen to a duration of accumulated thermal cycles at the maximum cycling temperature.
2. The microstructural changes of the Ti-15-3 matrix is the most likely explanation for the reduction in residual strength of the specimens and due to prolonged exposure to the higher temperatures used in this study.

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